

maturity by excavating and washing the soil in the 0-5, 5-10, and 10-25 cm layers. Roots were rewashed and dried at 60°C. Rooting density was expressed as weight of dry roots per unit volume of soil. Root weight index was total root weight per cm² soil surface in the entire (0-25 cm) root zone.

Soil moisture regime significantly affected root distribution (see table). Root weight index increased with water supply. Incorporation of straw significantly decreased the root weight index and rooting density in all three layers. However, in the surface (0-5 cm) layer, the fraction of total roots increased from 34% under no straw to 38% when 2% straw was incorporated, showing that higher soil reduction increased the fraction of the total roots in the surface layer.

Incorporation of straw also

Effect of soil moisture regime and straw incorporation on root growth and yield of rice. Ludhiana, India.

Treatment	Rooting density ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$) at indicated depth			Root weight index (mg/cm^2)	Yield (g/pot)
	0-5 cm deep	5-10 cm deep	10-25 cm deep		
<i>Moisture regime</i>					
Field capacity	482	415	157	7.3	107
Saturation	661	502	287	10.1	206
Submergence	995	567	377	13.5	234
<i>Straw treatment</i>					
No straw	891	728	329	13.0	235
1% straw	702	479	287	10.2	169
2% straw	538	277	203	7.1	143
CD (0.05)					
Moisture regime or straw	174	117	172	3.0	19

decreased the rice grain yield significantly. The grain yield was linearly related to the root weight index ($R^2 = 0.93$). The reduction in root growth and grain yield was probably due to the accumulation of toxic substances in the root zone, under highly reduced conditions

provided by the decomposition of added straw. This also appears to be the likely reason for significantly higher grain yield under submergence than under saturation, since the toxic substances will be better leached under continued submergence than under saturation. □

Influence of moisture regime on IR50

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An experiment was conducted on water needs of IR50 during summer and kharif 1985. Four irrigation treatments were evaluated: continuous submergence (5 cm), 5-cm depth to saturation, saturation up to and after heading and 5-cm water during heading (panicle initiation to flowering), and saturation at 25% depletion of available soil moisture (DASM). The experiment was in a randomized block design with eight replications.

IR50 yield and water use efficiency.

Treatment	1985 dry season (summer)			1985 wet season (kharif)		
	Total water applied (mm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water use efficiency	Total water applied (mm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Water use efficiency
Continuous submergence (5 cm)	1850	6.2	3.34	1399	6.4	4.55
Saturation to 5 cm	986	6.6	6.67	1141	6.6	5.75
Saturation up to and after heading and 5 cm during heading	1205	6.4	5.29	1055	6.2	5.88
Saturation at 25% DASM	620	5.7	9.18	685	5.5	8.06
CD at 5%		0.5			1.0	

During the dry season, irrigation to saturation to 5-cm depth consumed 47% of the water required by continuous submergence (see table). This trend continued in the wet season, with a saving of 18% of the irrigation

water. Irrigation to saturation at 25% DASM consumed the least irrigation water (620 mm in summer and 685 mm in wet season) and yield was reduced by only 11% (on the average) for a higher water use efficiency. □

P and K requirements of upland rice in eastern Uttar Pradesh

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We studied the effect of P and K on yield and yield components of rainfed upland rice variety IET7613 (85 d maturity) during 1985 at Faizabad. Soil was sandy loam with 22.5% field capacity and 4.6% wilting point of the 0-15 cm soil profile. Bulk density was

1.42 g/cm³. Total rainfall during the crop season was 920 mm with monthly distributions of 92 mm (Jun), 374 mm (Jul), 140 mm (Aug), 197 mm (Sep), and 117 mm (Oct). The rice crop faced 3 dry spells: 6 d during the first 14 d of Jul, 7 d during mid-Aug, and 11 d